

REVIEW ON IOT- ASSOCIATED WIDE-AREA WSN

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ABSTRACT - With the rapid advancement of Internet of Things innovation, there have been numerous applications connected with the Internet of Things. WSN is an assortment of exceptionally minuscule nodes which has acquired a high consideration of the scientists because of its different applications in various areas. The little devices, called the sensor nodes are sent in a cruel area and left unattended to report the boundaries of the climate, in light of the application consistently. The small nodes are compelled by the energy and consequently it becomes important to consume less energy by utilizing the means of clustering with the goal that the lifetime of the entire network can be drawn out. This paper reviews on IOT - associated wide-area WSN and different issues with respect to it.

Keywords: [Internet of Things, Wireless Sensor Network, wide-area, Mobile sensor.]

1. INTRODUCTION

The essential components representing things to come internet planned as Internet of Things (IoT) incorporate three significant parts which empower consistent correspondence. The first is the equipment which is comprised of sensors, actuators and implanted correspondence equipment like Radio Frequency Identification (RFID), Wireless Sensor Network (WSN), and so forth. The second is a middleware which performs on-request capacity and registering instruments for data investigation. What's more, the latter is a show of novel and straightforward perception and translation devices which can be widely gotten to on various stages and which can be intended for various applications. The arising IoT has a broadened application situation furnished with a wide scope of heterogeneous devices. As WSN likewise has a wide scope of utilization in the different working space and is additionally appropriate for longterm data acquisition, thus WSN will be the best sensor connecting gadget in the IoT climate. The WSN particularly comprises of disseminated independent sensors which checked natural or physical circumstances like temperature, pressure, sounds, and so on and passes their detected information through the way to the fundamental location. These ways are made by utilizing routing. The routing is an interaction to make a way between source hubs to the objective hub that cluster-based

routing algorithm shows better energy use rate when contrasted with the non-cluster routing algorithm.

Figure 1. Structure of Wireless sensor Network

For data analysis, presently founded on the heterogeneity and multidimensionality of the Internet of Things data, there are not many angles connected with data analysis in the business, like the substance and structure. What's more, the longterm advancement will definitely rely upon the profundity of data analysis abilities. The capacity of data analysis and data processing will decide how far the huge data way. Subsequently, the proposition of CEP innovation has enormously further developed the likelihood that this issue can be tackled rapidly and really. In any case, when the progression of occasions frames enormous data, there are numerous weaknesses in the ongoing strategies and procedures for really obtaining occasion pattern relationships. Focusing on the above issues and inadequacies, this paper plans and streamlining algorithm in view of Hadoop cluster stage K-Means clustering algorithm. The data, right off the bat, is handled continuously and afterward handled in the conventional K-Means clustering algorithm. Based on this, an algorithm for its enhancement is planned with the goal that the adequacy and proficiency of clustering of data are significantly gotten to the next level.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

1. Parag Kulkarni (2020) et.al proposed Experimental Evaluation of a Campus-deployed IoT Network using LoRa. The rise of the Internet of Things (IoT) has reclassified sensor networking with a remarkable increase in the number

of applications utilizing sensor technology in a myriad of domains. This has additionally upset the communication technology expected to arrange these sensors to take advantage of their true capacity. Short range remote advancements give high data rate and ordinarily work in the unlicensed band. Cell advancements then again give somewhat longer range, higher data rate and work in the authorized spectrum. The need to bridge the hole between these two, i.e., give a low expense and longer range arrangement with the capacity to interface huge number of geologically fanned out gadgets utilizing the unlicensed spectrum prompted the rise of Low Power Wide Area Networks (LPWAN). Long Range (LoRa), one of the LPWAN advances keeps on standing out given its open particular and prepared accessibility of off-the-rack hardware with cases of a few Kms of range in unforgiving testing conditions. In this paper they put these cases under test through broad estimations completed over a test-bed conveyed in a University grounds. The directed tests zeroed in on the connection quality and transmission execution in view of different boundaries, for example, the spreading factor (SF), coding rates (CR), transfer speed for various radio engendering situations. Discoveries from this study demonstrate the way that the reachable presentation can significantly fluctuate and prompts alert while fully trusting numbers as this can have suggestions for the IoT applications.

Merits

Findings from this study feature that the reachable exhibition can change incredibly contingent upon the organization situation and boundary configuration.

Demerits

The expense versus benefit compromise of such a way to deal with meets functional and business necessities.

2. J. P. García-Martín (2019) et.al proposed On the Combination of LR-WPAN and LPWA Technologies to Provide a Collaborative Wireless Solution for Diverse IoT. Low Power Wide Area (LPWA) Normalization organic entities have embraced an extraordinary exertion in determining the reasonable low-power wireless technologies to be utilized. IEEE 802.15 Working Group (WG), alluding to wireless specialty networks, proposes a wide range of guidelines and revisions covering different application situations in regards to communication range and data rate inside Industrial, Scientific and Medical (ISM) unlicensed groups. The primary explanation is on the grounds that they can associate gadgets that are a lot further separated than in customary Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs), and with extremely low power utilization. To be sure, LPWA networks are being sent and, simultaneously, they coincide in the ongoing worldview with a wide range of wireless frameworks for IoT. The frameworks are planned together and take profit of the better of every one, and all out exhibitions are upgraded by a legitimate plan of their configuration boundaries. An answer for join IEEE 802.15.4g and Narrow Band-IoT (NB-IoT) technologies is investigated and carried out. Through the expansion of hubs with twofold availability, it is feasible to enhance the communication links utilizing a few legitimacy figures. Three potential NB-IoT handsets have been tested with satisfactory outcomes.

Merits

A CH can change the favoured communication link at runtime, for example, in the event that it recognizes various retransmissions on the 802.15.4.

Demerits

An adaptive learning technique select the best links will likewise be the not objectives.

3. J. D. Trigo (2020) et.al proposed Patient Tracking in a Multi-Building, Tunnel-Connected Hospital Complex. Realizing their locations are keys for a sound preparation of intra-hospital transports as well as assets the executives. This is much more pivotal in big hospital edifices, contained a few buildings often connected through tunnels. The framework use Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) communication technologies, for example, Long Range Wide-Area Network (LoRaWAN) and Near Field Communication (NFC). The locations of the LoRaWAN hubs were chosen in view of a few factors, including the situation of the tunnels, buildings administrations and medical hardware. Once the locations were set, a LoRaWAN radio inclusion studio was performed. The principal conclusion drawn is that only one LoRaWAN gateway would be sufficient to make all over progress LoRaWAN hubs conveyed. A second one would be expected for underground inclusion. In addition, a remote, private cloud infrastructure along with a versatile application was made to deal with the information produced. On-field tests were performed to survey the specialized possibility of the framework. The application gives on-demand ICU patients' development flow around the complex. Albeit intended for the ICUadmitted patients' context, the framework could be effortlessly extrapolated to other use cases.

Merits

The application outfits the client with on-request ICU patient advancement stream around the complex.

Demerits

The fundamental thought could be extrapolated to different contexts - either medical or non-medical.

4. C. Cheng (2012) et.al proposed Three-Dimensional Location-Based IPv6 Addressing for Wireless Sensor Networks in Smart Grid. Smart grid is one of the main applications of the Internet of Things (IoT) for environmental manageability and energy effectiveness issues lately. IP-based wireless sensor networks (IP-WSNs) are considered as one of the promising wireless communication technologies applied in smart grid for giving unavoidable prerequisite for conveying intermediaries. In addition, the IPv6 Internet has turned into an unavoidable pattern for all-IP communication in view of its huge address space and others benefits over IPv4. MPIPA uses three-dimensional locations directions to dole out every node an interesting spatial IPv6 address in view of grouping strategies and sweep line conspire. In addition, Assignment Success Rate (ASR) is utilized in this paper to assess the likelihood that relegates novel IP address to nodes successfully. The simulation results show that MPIPA empowers more than 8,000 nodes to be doled out IP address successfully when ASR is still nearly 90%.

Merits

MPIPA uses three-dimensional locations directions to dole out every node a special spatial IPv6 address in view of grouping strategies and sweep line plot.

Demerits

The mobility in WSNs turns into the interest issues because of a few reasons for changing organization topology.

5. M. Schadhauer (2021) et.al proposed Spectrum Segmentation Techniques for Edge-RAN Decoding in Telemetry-Based IoT Networks. The potential fields of application for little sensor nodes are colossal nevertheless developing quick. Particularly in the extent of Low Power Wide Area (LPWA) communications, this situation brings about high computational exertion and complexity for the beneficiary side to see the signs of interest. Thusly, this paper examines means to an adequate segmentation of get spectra for an incomplete spectrum trade between base stations of telemetry-based IoT sensor networks. The particular exchange of in-phase and quadrature (IQ) data could work with stream consolidating strategies to veil out impedances amongst different methodologies. This will further develop decoding rates significantly under extreme operation conditions and at the same time limit the expected data volume. To adapt to the high data rates despite everything empower base station collaboration, particularly in wirelessly connected collector network networks, different channel bank methods and block changes are inspected, to partition telemetry spectra into unmistakable frequency sub-stations. Operational constraints for the spectral decomposition are given and different channel philosophies are presented. At last, reasonable measurements are laid out. These measurements will survey the exhibition of the introduced spectrum segmentation plans with the end goal of a particular halfway exchange between sensor network receivers.

Merits

Given their high selectivity capacity while as yet displaying attainable computational complexity and overhead.

Demerits

Not give adequate stop band attenuation to an adequate energy containment and minimal spectral spillage.

6. W. -T. Sung (2019) et.al proposed LoRa-based Internet of Things Secure Localization System and Application. Lately, with the fast improvement of organization security, multi-sensor fusion computing, and LoRa technology, the localization system of a national security monitoring system has evidently turned into a vital piece of technology upgrade, and the different strategies applied to the LoRa wireless sensor security localization design are slowly acquiring attention as their incredible advancement potential is introduced. Consequently, lately, numerous colleges have concentrated on automation designing and communication technology domains in succession. As far as the improvement of traditional wireless sensor design systems, numerous specialists and researchers have concentrated on significant localization calculations, and got great results. Nonetheless, in comparison to the advancement utilizing network security, multi-sensor fusion computing, and LoRa technology to integrate traditional national security monitoring systems, the information research manpower is

less, and this secure localization computing technology affects the improvement of national security monitoring systems. Subsequently, the construction of a national security monitoring system utilizing network security, multi-sensor fusion computing, and LoRa technology, as evolved in this review, will have explicit and meaningful contributions. This undertaking computes parcels and contrasts other improvement strategies and ZigBee, and the outcomes demonstrate the way that reliability can be increased by around 45%, hence, meeting the expected unit system specifications. The discoveries of this study will be developed into a national security monitoring system stage with practical popularization values, and related results will be distributed in international diaries.

Merits

The LoRa IoT f giving organization topology self-configuration, expanding routing productivity, revealing organization inclusion quality to the deployer.

Demerits

A secure node location system for the IoT applications with threatening potential outcomes is a key issue.

7. M. I. Nashiruddin (2020) et.al proposed Designing LoRaWAN Internet of Things Network for Smart Manufacture in Batam Island. Today, the implementation of industry 4.0 is expanding in different areas of the planet, and it is creating the utilization of Internet of Things (IoT) technology in assembling, otherwise called smart assembling. In any case, one of the principal challenges confronted is picking the most fitting organization connectivity technology. One of the most widely utilized is LoRaWAN in light of the fact that it enjoys a few benefits with its long-distance advantage, low expense, interference opposition or Smart Manufacture, which connecting the noise, temperature, carbon emission, and asset tracking device. Batam Island was picked as the object of examination since it is a selective economic zone with the biggest integrated industrial home in Indonesia. To convey smart manufacture administrations in Batam Island that value of 7 of the Receive Signal Strength Indicator Value (RSSI) > - 123 dBm and SINR value of - 30 dB with a typical throughput distribution of 18.82 kbps.

Merits

The Smart Manufacture for temperature, noise, carbon emission, and assets tracking in view of LoRaWAN can apply in Batam Island.

Demerits

Batam Island causes the expansion of entryways expected to cover regions not yet covered by nine passages.

8. S. Ali et.al proposed Energy Recovery from Microstrip Passive Circuits. A thermoelectric generator (TEG) in view of the Seebeck impact rule is utilized, which converts a piece of the power dispersed into intensity to dc electrical power. An answer planning the TEG with the microstrip circuit is proposed, and configuration rules to update the recovered power keeping a nice segregation between the RF signal and the TEG structure are given. As will be shown, under moderate applied signal powers of only 1-5 W, the degrees of recuperated power in microstrip separated circuits can strike. As a demonstrator circuit, a compromise

contraption illustrated by an installed microstrip bandpass channel for WiMAX applications and a TEG is planned, produced, and portrayed (thermal and electrically). Various situations are considered, contingent upon frequency and thermal loads. For an applied inband CW input signal power of 2 W at 3.48 GHz, a recuperated power of around 250 μ W has been continuously provided to the electrical burden. A few perspectives, like proficiency and future upgrades, are likewise examined.

Merits

From microwave passive components working under moderate power signals, an observable measure of power can be recuperated and in this way, being reused.

Demerits

Recovered power can't be worked on by attempting to increase the intensity flux through the TEG.

9. E. Sisinni (2018) et.al proposed Enhanced flexible LoRaWAN node for Industrial IoT. The Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) is presenting the IoT approach in the industrial automation world, making ready to creative services for further developing effectiveness, reliability and availability of industrial cycles and items. The IIoT exploits the collection of huge measure of data through (wireless) links connecting smart sensors appended to the system of interest. Low Power Wide Area Networks arose as a practical solution for carrying out private cellular like communications. Specifically, an upgraded node is proposed as a building block of IIoT-empowered industrial wireless networks. It offers new highlights: it acts as a customary node; it can go about as a gateway toward legacy/unique (wired) networks; and it can expand LoRaWAN inclusion going about as a range extender (for example a solitary bounces forwarder). After a short outline of LoRa and LoRaWAN, the paper manages the elements of the acknowledged node, taking advantage of economically accessible hardware. Specifically, the range extender capacity of communicating replicas of approaching messages is tested for various transmission delays.

Merits

The range extender ability of sending replicas of approaching messages is tested for various transmission delays.

Demerits

The e-Node functionalities not stretched out to act as a Proxy for IIoT applications.

10. M. Provoost (2019) et.al proposed DingNet: A Self-Adaptive Internet-of-Things Exemplar. The Internet-of-Things gives an empowering layer to smart cities applications. Nonetheless, engineering such applications is trying as these systems ordinarily consist of a complex conveyed infrastructure that is dependent upon different vulnerabilities. Self-adaptation can then offer a solution. In this paper, they proposed the DingNet model to help research on self adaptation in the IoT area. The DingNet test system upholds analysts and architects to design and break down self-adaptive smart city applications that expand upon the IoT. They illustrated how they utilized the test system to concentrate on a common self-adaptation issue where mobile motes dynamically adjust their power settings to

guarantee dependable and energy proficient communication of sensor data that is sent from the motes to the application. They are at present testing the exemplar for bigger scope adaptation situations, as the model about cycling through trajectories with great air quality and routing vehicles in a city to diminish air pollution at city level. Later on they intend to improve the test system by gathering data from field trials and utilize this data to bring the test system as close as conceivable to the genuine setting. They trust that the exploration community will utilize the DingNet model to assess and analyze research propels in adaptive and self-overseeing systems, and drive their examination further. The model that is executed in Java is openly accessible for experimentation.

Merits

The DingNet test system upholds analysts and specialists to design and break down self-adaptive smart city applications that expand upon the IoT.

Demerits

The test systems by gathering data from field examinations and utilize this data to bring the test system as close are impractical to the genuine setting.

11. Y. Rong (2020) et.al proposed Staged text clustering algorithm based on K-means and hierarchical agglomeration clustering. Text clustering is significant technologies in the field of text mining, which can successfully help individuals, see large-scale text, and simultaneously as a compelling pre-processing step, it likewise gives a corpus design to additional text analysis. Text clustering separates assets into significant clusters as per corresponding norms, with the goal that the similarity between texts in one cluster is higher than the similarity between texts in various clusters. At present, text as semi-structured data, the principal clustering methods are: partition method, hierarchical method, density-based method, network based method, model-based method. The organized text clustering algorithm SC-KH proposed in this paper utilizes Canopy algorithm to further develop the K-means algorithm's concerns about the underlying k value and the selection of clustering focuses. The k classes acquired by the K-means algorithm can be viewed as the constraint classes in the clustering system of the hierarchical agglomeration algorithm, which somewhat compensates for the irrevocable imperfections simultaneously and decreases the time complexity of the algorithm. In any case, toward the start of the SC-KH algorithm, it is as yet important to set the two thresholds T1 and T2 physically. The setting of the threshold likewise influences the nature of clustering, so this has additionally turned into the direction of additional exploration later on.

Merits

The SC-KH algorithm integrated with multiple clustering algorithms makes accomplished a superior difference.

Demerits

The threshold likewise influences the nature of clustering, so this has additionally turned into the direction.

12. M. A. Mondal (2019) et.al proposed Identifying Traffic Congestion Pattern using K-means Clustering Technique. With increase in urbanization and socio-economical growth,

the number of vehicles in significant metropolitan cities is expanding step by step. It gains constant street traffic information and classifies the different street segments in view of traffic density and average speed of vehicles. In this manner, traffic congestion is turning into a main pressing issue of metropolitan cities everywhere. This results in enormous air pollution, loss of important time and money of residents. Subsequently, traffic congestion monitoring of various street segments is extremely fundamental for examining the issue related with smooth versatility. Distinguishing the risky street segments inside the city is one of the significant positions for the transport power to evaluate the street condition. That will help the government agencies or policy creators to streamline traffic rules and regulations. This work distinguishes traffic congestion design which can characterize the different street segments in light of traffic density and average speed of vehicles. The proposed system utilizes KMeans clustering algorithm to sort the different street segments. The system will help the transport authorities or policy producers to plan and design traffic management rules and regulations. It likewise helps in decision making in regards to regardless of whether further infrastructure is expected to adapt to the congestion.

Merits

The system will help the transport authorities or policy creators to plan and design traffic management rules and regulations.

Demerits

This results in huge air pollution, loss of significant time and money of residents.

13. A. Mortezaezhad (2019) et.al proposed Big-Data Clustering with Genetic Algorithm. In this paper they managed a classical issue of classification in Big-Data. They proposed to utilize a GA based algorithm to consequently find the cluster numbers and utilized a distance based association component. In every chromosome, which represents a normal clustering, the number of clusters is picked randomly. In every generation, a succession of actions including the calculation of the wellness function, applying the crossover and mutation administrators, and nearby pursuit is conducted and the chromosomes with best wellness are ignored to the future. As a significant processing step, they dispose of those clusters without any individuals. They rehash this cycle up to arriving at a realized generation number. Toward the end, the fittest chromosome is the solution of our algorithm. In is evident that for the elitist clustering, they ordinarily have a right number of clusters and the most distance among them. The proposed GA has novel features in the design of cross-over and mutation administrators. The exhibition of the proposed algorithm is tested on different data sets and our evaluations demonstrate the way that they can beat notable methods like EGGAC. Our numerical simulations show that the proposed algorithm is very reality and possess a decent exhibition on synthetic 1.000.000-example data. It is feasible to have a quicker algorithm utilizing feature selection and feature reduction conspires that they didn't attempt them here. They likewise can utilize a quicker algorithm to set the underlying population than the notable k-means algorithm they utilized here.

Merits

Numerical simulations show that the proposed algorithm is very reality and possess a decent presentation on synthetic data.

Demerits

Not conceivable to have a quicker algorithm utilizing feature selection and feature reduction plans.

14. R. Bensaid (2020) et.al proposed Fuzzy C-Means based Clustering Algorithm in WSNs for IoT Applications. Energy effectiveness in Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) - based Internet of Things (IoT) systems is an exceptionally difficult issue since IoT is turning out to be more perplexing because of its large scale sending. In this cutting edge age, the critical improvement in the field of Internet of Things (IoT) has made the human existence more developed. It has acquired prosperity the existences of all person. The concept of IoT was extended in lined up with Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs). A WSN is made out of n sensor nodes dispersed randomly over a geographical area. Individual sensor nodes can detect, measure, and assemble information from the environment in light of the neighborhood predefined decision process. The detected data sent to a base station is known as sink node. A WSN-based IoT application consists of a bunch of autonomous sensors, ready to take measurements on the environment to construct a worldwide perspective on the controlled area. In this paper, they proposed a novel FCM-based clustering algorithm to further develop the organization lifetime and conserve energy in WSNs for IoT applications. They conducted a near report between the proposed protocol and LEACH with regards to the organization lifetime, the first and last node dead and the leftover energy. Results showed that the proposed FCM based protocol outflanks LEACH.

Merits

The proposed FCM method further develops the organization lifetime by improving the residual energy by half.

Demerits

IoT is turning out to be more complicated because of its large scale arrangement.

15. S. A. Aboalner (2019) et.al proposed Energy-Aware Task Allocation Algorithm Based on Transitive Cluster-Head Selection for IoT Networks. Internet of Things (IoT) is a concept that empowers different actual items and methods of communication to accomplish a specific task by exchanging information. IoT has carried the potential chances to have a smart home, environmental monitoring, security observation, healthcare, and business applications, which contribute to increase the nature of our life and develop the world's economy. IoT takes advantage of basic technologies to make these articles a lot smarter, for example, wireless sensor networks, applications, and Internet protocols, ubiquitous and embedded devices. Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) become an infrastructure for IoT applications. IoT involves sensor nodes and other middle devices that are connected by means of the Internet through broad Internet technologies. A task allocation component is proposed in this paper utilizing a clustering procedure with energy threshold levels. Administration is partitioned into tasks, and the task is

separated into subtasks that are disseminated on the cluster that has the most elevated energy of the relative multitude of clusters. The proposed solution checked great outcome similar with previous examinations in light of the task allocation strategy. The lifetime of the organization in the proposed algorithm beats the previous methodology. Moreover, the proposed approach was fit for finishing a greater number of jobs than the current methodology. Hence, this demonstrates the upgrades that are embraced in this review improved the organization execution productively.

Merits

The upgrades that are embraced in this review improved the organization execution productively.

Demerits

The primary difficulties of this moving technology are energy consumption.

CONCLUSION

Clustering schemes are better routing protocols appropriate for huge scope wireless sensor networks and robust at presence of topological changes brought about by node movements, Node disappointments, and node inclusion or expulsion. This paper reviews on IOT - associated wide-area WSN and different issues with respect to it. Right now, there are countless superb clustering routing protocols and just survey a few delegates of them in this paper. The greater part of the research on clustering in WSNs mainly focuses on energy consumption, network lifetime, data latency, and non-functional goals, like data integrity.

REFERENCES

- [1]. P. Kulkarni, Q. O. A. Hakim and A. Lakas, "Experimental Evaluation of a Campus-Deployed IoT Network Using LoRa," in *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 20, no. 5, pp. 2803-2811, 1 March, 2020, doi: 10.1109/JSEN.2019.2953572.
- [2]. J. P. García-Martín and A. Torralba, "On the Combination of LR-WPAN and LPWA Technologies to Provide a Collaborative Wireless Solution for Diverse IoT," 2019 International Conference on Wireless and Mobile Computing, Networking and Communications (WiMob), 2019, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/WiMOB.2019.8923566.
- [3]. J. D. Trigo et al., "Patient Tracking in a Multi-Building, Tunnel-Connected Hospital Complex," in *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 20, no. 23, pp. 14453-14464, 1 Dec.1, 2020, doi: 10.1109/JSEN.2020.3007593.
- [4]. C. Cheng, C. Chuang and R. Chang, "Three-Dimensional Location-Based IPv6 Addressing for Wireless Sensor Networks in Smart Grid," 2012 IEEE 26th International Conference on Advanced Information Networking and Applications, 2012, pp. 824-831, doi: 10.1109/AINA.2012.42.
- [5]. M. Schadhauer, J. Robert, A. Heuberger and B. Edler, "Spectrum Segmentation Techniques for Edge-RAN Decoding in Telemetry-Based IoT Networks," 2021 IEEE International IOT, Electronics and Mechatronics Conference (IEMTRONICS), 2021, pp. 1-8, doi: 10.1109/IEMTRONICS52119.2021.9422584.
- [6]. W. -T. Sung, S. -J. Hsiao, S. -Y. Wang and J. -H. Chou, "LoRa-based Internet of Things Secure Localization System

and Application," 2019 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man and Cybernetics (SMC), 2019, pp. 1672-1677, doi: 10.1109/SMC.2019.8913875.

- [7]. M. I. Nashiruddin and S. Winalisa, "Designing LoRaWAN Internet of Things Network for Smart Manufacture in Batam Island," 2020 8th International Conference on Information and Communication Technology (ICoICT), 2020, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/ICoICT49345.2020.9166426.
- [8]. X. -W. Wu, W. Farag, S. Ali and S. Kulkarni, "An Efficient Security Scheme for the Internet of Things with Resource-Constrained Devices," 2019 IEEE 10th Annual Ubiquitous Computing, Electronics & Mobile Communication Conference (UEMCON), 2019, pp. 0679-0685, doi: 10.1109/UEMCON47517.2019.8993102.
- [9]. E. Sisinni, D. F. Carvalho, P. Ferrari, A. Flammini, D. R. C. Silva and I. M. D. Da Silva, "Enhanced flexible LoRaWAN node for industrial IoT," 2018 14th IEEE International Workshop on Factory Communication Systems (WFCS), 2018, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/WFCS.2018.8402367.
- [10]. M. Provoost and D. Weyns, "DingNet: A Self-Adaptive Internet-of-Things Exemplar," 2019 IEEE/ACM 14th International Symposium on Software Engineering for Adaptive and Self-Managing Systems (SEAMS), 2019, pp. 195-201, doi: 10.1109/SEAMS.2019.00033.
- [11]. Y. Rong and Y. Liu, "Staged text clustering algorithm based on K-means and hierarchical agglomeration clustering," 2020 IEEE International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Computer Applications (ICAICA), 2020, pp. 124-127, doi: 10.1109/ICAICA50127.2020.9182394.
- [12]. M. A. Mondal and Z. Rehena, "Identifying Traffic Congestion Pattern using K-means Clustering Technique," 2019 4th International Conference on Internet of Things: Smart Innovation and Usages (IoT-SIU), 2019, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/IoT-SIU.2019.8777729.
- [13]. A. Mortezaezhad and E. Daneshifar, "Big-Data Clustering with Genetic Algorithm," 2019 5th Conference on Knowledge Based Engineering and Innovation (KBEI), 2019, pp. 702-706, doi: 10.1109/KBEI.2019.8735076.
- [14]. R. Bensaid, M. Ben Said and H. Boujemaa, "Fuzzy C-Means based Clustering Algorithm in WSNs for IoT Applications," 2020 International Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing (IWCMC), 2020, pp. 126-130, doi: 10.1109/IWCMC48107.2020.9148077.
- [15]. S. A. Aboalner, "Energy-Aware Task Allocation Algorithm Based on Transitive Cluster-Head Selection for IoT Networks," 2019 12th International Conference on Developments in eSystems Engineering (DeSE), 2019, pp. 176-179, doi: 10.1109/DeSE.2019.00041.